

Agricultural Development under the Five Year Plan in Madurai District (1950-1961)

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ABSTRACT

The Department of Agriculture is to improve the economic status of the farmer by doubling the production and tripling the income. For Second Green Revolution Agriculture Department has formulated various policies and strategies to achieve equitable, competitive and sustainable growth in Agriculture Crops. Madurai District is mainly agrarian with an average rainfall of 874.5mm . Paddy, Millet, Pulses, Cotton are the major crops cultivated in Madurai District. Periyar-Vaigai canal is the main source of irrigation. The Government policy and objectives have been to ensure stability in agricultural production and to increase the agricultural production in a sustainable manner to meet the food requirement of growing population and also to meet the raw material needs of agro based industries, thereby providing employment opportunities to the rural population. Madurai has all along been one of the city with a creditable performance in agricultural production with the farmers relatively more responsive and receptive to changing technologies and market forces. The Government took initiate the steps for expansion in irrigation facilities, availability for production technology especially for small scale industries. The transport communication market infrastructure and processing facility for high value, crops should be strengthened around the Madurai district.

Key Words: Agriculture, Crops, Madurai, Irrigation, Government.

Introduction

The economy of Madurai District has developed greatly as a consequence of First and Second Five year Plans. The Excessive dependence on agriculture by the people for their livelihood has dwindled through the plans. Agriculture continues to be the mainstay of the people of the district. The Plans particularly the Second Five Year Plan aimed at starting new industries in various rural centres with a view to raising the standard of living of the common man. In the field of power development, irrigation, community development to the district has recorded palpable progress. The achievements made tremendous changes in all rural areas during the first and second plans.

Agriculture

There has been increase in the area under cultivation of different crops in the district during decade. The net sown area in the district went up from 1,205,261 acres in 1950-51 to 1,391,885 acres at the end of the first plan and 1,391,464 acres at the end of the second plan. The area under paddy cultivation has gone up from 316,436 acres in 1950-51 to 346,996 acres in 1955-56 and 400,044 in 1960-61. In production of different crops has also increased during the plans and this revealed by the following figures for important crops. It has been roughly estimated that the district has reached self-sufficiency in food grain production from a deficit status which it had at the beginning as well as at the end of the First Plan. The number of agricultural depots has increased from 18 to 30 during the Second Plan period. During 1956-61, six seed farms have started functioning and seeds grown distributed throughout the Madurai District.³ The Japanese method of cultivation first introduced in 1953 was followed in 20,000 acres at the end of First Plan and 282,000 acres at the end of the Second Plan. During the Second Plan period 290,000 tons of Chemical fertilizers were distributed, and these were used in 476,409 acres of land resulting in additional yield of food grains to the tune 63,326 tons. The following statement shows the progress in the preparation and use of compost manure in rural and urban areas of the district during the decade.

During the First Plan period 113 tons of green manure were prepared. These were used in 6,355 acres and resulted in extra production of 578 tons. During the Second Plan 368 tons of green manure were prepared. They were used in 55,250 acres and resulted in 5,520 tons of increased production. During the Second Plan 10 tractors were given on a rental basis and over 15,000 improved agricultural implements were distributed at subsidized rates.⁵

Production of Chief Crops in the District

S.NO	CROPS	PRODUCTION IN TOOLS		
		1950-51	1955-56	1960-61
1	Rice	230,250	217,230	252,560
2	Cholam	82,750	108,450	133,610
3	Cumbu	9,180	17,100	16,850
4	Ragi	16,740	21,330	20,920
5	Groundnut	53,690	71,080	119,660
6	Sugarcane	295,900	275,470	425,,8
7	Cotton(bales)	30,290	49,780	44,040 ²

Progress in the use of Compost Manure

S.No	Areas	Prepared In Tons	Used In Tons	Resultant Extra Production Of Food Grains In Tons
1, Rural Areas				
	First Plan Period	68,636	13,726	1,716
	Second Plan Period	142,690	25,538	7,134
2, Urban Areas				
	First Plan Period	143,626	28,724	3,590
	Second Plan Period	134,355	26,871	6,718 ⁴

Plant Production Schemes

Plant production schemes are very important for agricultural development. The progress in the distribution and use of insecticides during the Plans are given overleaf. Schemes to improve fruit gardens were taken up in Kodaikanal, Dindigul and Periyakulam taluks. A fruit garden was established at Periyakulam during the First Plan period 1951-56, 167,481 fruit seedlings were distributed.

Insecticides distributed during the Plan Periods

S.No	Details of Progress	First Plan	Second Plan
1	Insecticides distributed in tons	208	574
2	Area of Land in which used in areas	78,321	337,447
3	Additional Production in tons	3,914	16,894

. During the Second Plan the scheme was intensified. For those growing new fruit trees a long-term loan of Rs.300 per acre was given and to renew the existing gardens a short-term loan of Rs.65 was given. During the Second Plan period steps were taken to augment production through modern methods. Tractors oil engines and electric motor pump sets were supplied on hirepurchase system. Dusters, Sprayers and modern agricultural implements like Bose ploughs were distributed to riots at subsidised rates.⁶

Forest

The forestarea of the district is around four lakh acres. During the last 10 years in Madurai north region, 1,060 acres of pasture were developed at a cost of Rs.15,700. Cashew cultivation was made in 60 acres at a cost of Rs.3,000. During the last 10 years teak and other trees were planted in an area of 60 acres at the cost of Rs.1,29,700. Soft wood trees were grown during the plans in 732 acres at a cost of Rs.75,600. Wattle and other trees came to be cultivated in 5,752 acres during the Second Plan period at a cost of Rs.3.79 lakhs. Soil conservation schemes were also taken up during the plans.⁷ To prevent soil at a cost of Rs.2.44 lakhs. Steps were also taken to preserve wild life in the forest areas. Lac producing centres in three places were opened during the Second Plan Period. Lac production has increased from 33,390 pounds in 1958-59 to 38,883 pounds in 1960-61. In Madurai south range tamarind trees have been planted in 320 acres at a cost of Rs.5,800.

Animal Husbandry

The cattle population of Madurai district has increased from 22,72,082 in 1951 to 25,25,000 in 1961. During the First Plan period. The Premium Scheme, the Cattle Distribution

Scheme and the scheme for Artificial Insemination centres were implemented. A village centre was started at Toppampatti where stud bulls were bred and medical aid was given. There are 13 key village centres in the district and 5 artificial insemination centres. During the Second Plan period artificial insemination was administered on 9,050 cows, and 520 calves were born of them. To protect calves the Government gave Rs10 per calf and 750 calves were thus protected during the Second Plan period. Extension centres have been opened in eight village in the district. Government aid was also given to the ryots to the extent of 50% for purchasing stud bulls. For improving poultry keeping methods four centres were opened in the district during the Plan in rural areas. At the cost of Rs.17,500 each buildings have been constructed at the Gandhigram and Kodaikanal poultry units. To prevent communicable diseases among cattle two mobile centres have started functioning in the district. There are 21 veterinary hospitals and dispensaries in the Madurai district besides 8 first-aid centres.

Fisheries

The Madurai district has no coastline and depends on inland waters for fishers development. During the First Plan period experimental fish yards were opened at Madurai, Kallupatti, Vadugapatti, and Kodaikanal. Seven tanks were taken over by the Government in Madurai and Nilakottaitaluks during this period. Schemes for the development and exploitation of fishers in Periar Lake and Vaigai Reservoir were also made at a cost of 1.5 lakhs. Fingerlings were introduced in big tanks like the Theppakulam tank at Madurai and other irrigation tanks in Thirumangalamtaluk. Rural Demonstration Units were opened in several tanks south of Vaigai River. The number of fishers distributed for the purchases of multiplication in the district was 70 lakhs during the Second Plan period. Nearly 9 lakh fishes were let into the Vaigai Reservoir during 1956-61. Good quality fishes are distributed at subsidised rates. During the two Plans loans totalling to Rs.17,750 were given to fishermen through the three Co-operative Societies to purchase nylon nets and threads and to get mechanised boats through hire-purchase system. For Dindigul municipality a loan of Rs.11,870 was given for improving the fish Market.⁸

Co-Operative Societies

The Progress has been achieved in the field of co-operation during the decade. Roughly 83.5 percent of the villages came under co-operative fold in 1955-56 and all the villages are

covered by it. The percentage of persons who came under the co-operative fold was 23.6 in 1950-51 and now it has increased to 66.7. At the end of the First Plan, there were 846 Village Credit Societies and during the Second Plan period, 122 new societies were formed, thus raising the total to 968. During 1955-56, loans to agriculturists amounted to Rs.81 lakhs and in 1960-61 it was Rs.253 lakhs. During the four years 1957-61, aid amounting to Rs. 61,374 has been given to 286 co-operative societies. Aid amounting to Rs.83,920 was given to the District Central Co-operative Bank during the past five years. During the First Plan period, there were 6 Co-operative Sales Societies. There more societies were started during the Second Plan period and now there are nine Co-operative Sales Societies. These societies received loans to the tune of Rs.1,72,450 and aid of Rs.45,775 during the past five years. The Agricultural Banks got a loan amount of Rs. 3.30 lakhs and monetary aid of Rs.1.34 lakhs for building godowns. Sixteen sakes depots have been constructed so far. The Government have taken shares to the value of Rs. 65,000 in 10 agricultural banks. Full finance scheme was first introduced in 1959 in Tirupparankundram Development Block. During 1959-60, short term loans of Rs.894 lakhs and medium term loans of Rs.5.66 lakhs were given to members of agricultural co-operative banks.¹⁰ The number of agricultural banks in the districts increased from 9 to 43 during 1957 to 1961 and the number of members in them went to from 4,364, to 41,935. Since 1959-60, credit distributing unions were started under the Plan. Seven such union in 1959-60 and two in 1960-61, were started in the district. There were seven Land Mortgage Banks in 1955-56 and three more were opened during the Second Plan period. Milk Supply Co-operative Societies from 162 in 1955-56 to 196 in 1960-61. Milk production has gone up in these societies from 2,741 to 6,305 Madras measures during the Second Plan period. Loans and grants were given to these societies too. From 97, the number of weavers' co-operative societies has gone up to 105 during the planning decade Government help to these societies was rendered as follows Monthly aid towards rebates in sale Rs.18,79,885, Loans Rs. Rs.3,21,525, Contribution to share capital Rs.1,48,339 and Loans for building houses Rs.8,75,300.¹¹ A cooperative training centre was established at Tirunagerlin 1956. A Co-operative Farming Society was established in Valandur in 1956. During the Second Plan period, three more co-operative farms came into existence. Four Co operative Housing Societies during the First Plan periods and 37 co-operative Housing Societies during the Second plan period came into existence and now, in all, there are 78 Housing Co-operative Societies in the district.Ten GramdanSarvodaya Co-operative Societies have been formed in this district and the Government have sanctioned them a sum of Rs. 6,28,000 to be utilised in a period of 5 years.¹²

Community Development

The district has been divided into 34 blocks. At the end of second plan there were ten stage 1 blocks, 14 stage 11 blocks and two pre extension blocks. Loan facilities were given to the riots for purchasing agriculture implements for installing pump sets for digging wells etcetera. During the first plan, 292 wells were dug and the three overhead tanks were installed under your scheme to increase drinking water facilities. During the second plan, 882 wells were dug and three seven overhead tanks were installed. The schemes completed with the help of the public in cash under kind during the plans are as follows: installations of overhead tanks 14, workers small wells 448, roads 766. The extension program under agriculture is designed to augment productions by distributions of improved seeds and chemical fertilizers. By the use of improved agricultural implements and by the adoption of new methods of cultivation and agriculture department is attached to each block and the requirements of seeds besides etc of the riots in the block is. From the report the advantage of Japanese method of cultivation is propagated and riots are encouraged to adopt this method so as to get increase in production during the two plan periods the entire district has been covered by panchayats.¹³ The total number of panchayats constituted in the district is 856. Constituted in the district is 856.

Irrigation

The total area under irrigation in the district has increased from 431,500 acres in 1950-51 to 442,053 acres in 1955-56 and to 494,402 acres in 1960-61. The Vaigai Reservoir is an important irrigation project of the plans. A sum of rupees 83.41 lakhs and rupees 174 lakhs were spent during the First and Second Plans for this project. The capacity of this reservoir is 68,000 lakhs cubic feet. The length of the dam is 11,675 feet and its height is 110 feet. Irrigational facilities are provided by this project to Thirumangalam and Melur taluks of Ramanathapuram districts.¹⁴ A 17 1/2 mile-long Canal has been constructed in Thirumangalam taluk to provide facilities for 10,00 acres of land. Water was let out from reservoir in 1958. During 1959-60, 11,884 acres of land were irrigated. Since July 1960 a total area of 10,384 acres got irrigational facilities through the Thirumangalam canal. By the lowering of the water-shed cutting at Thekkady in Periyar Reservoir at a cost of Rs. 25 lakhs, 4,000 acres of land are benefited. Towards minor irrigation works, a sum of rupees 830 lakhs was spent. During the last 10 years the number of minor works completed was 188. An ayacut of 32,980 acres was brought under the cultivation through this and the additional increase in food production is estimated at about 6,120 tons. For

constructions of filter points, a loan of Rs. 2.55 lacs was given during the First Plan period. Over 150 wells were dug. During the Second Plan period 122 filter point wells were dug. In 1950-51 548 oil Engines under 7 to 8 electric pump sets were functioning in the district and they increased in 1960-61 to 1,096 and 6,416 respectively.¹⁵

Area under irrigation through various sources

S.NO	Source of Irrigation	Area Under Irrigation in acres		
		1950-51	1955-56	1960-61
1	Government canals	18,900	136,385	153,636
2	Tanks	95,400	131,849	154,458
3	Wells-sole irrigation	150,300	165,165	178,127
4	Other sources	3,900	8,656	8,181
Total		431,500	442,053	494,402¹⁶

That’s against the provisions of rupees 570 lacs for irrigation during the ten years in the district on amount of rupees 838 lacs was spent.

Power

With a view to meet the growing power requirements of the district the Periyar Hydro Electric schemes was taken up and was completed in the record time of three years. The first unit of 35,000 K.W. In the powerhouse was taken up in 1955 and was commissioned in 1958. The powerhouse is generating its full installed capacity of 105, 000 K.W. This was the first Hydro Electric Station in the district. The project was designed to utilize the discharge from the Periyar lake below the exiting tunnel where a head of about 1,230 feet was available for power protection. The cost of the project is Rs.10.09 crores. The capacity of the project can be increased to 140, 000 K.W. The Thermal stations are the Samayanallur completed in 1951, meets the short-fall in the protections of power during summer. The second unit of this Thermal stations was commenced in 1951 and completed in 1954. The installed capacity of

this stations is 14,000 kilowatts. For a good distributions and augmentations of power supply the transmissions lines of the Periyar-Theni- Madurai 110 K. W. ¹⁷ double line were laid during the Second Plan. The following statement shows the progress of the district in the field of Power Distribution during the plans.

Progress of Electrification in the District

S.NO	Content	First Plan Period	Second Plan Period
1	Number of villages electrified	55	321
2	Number of electric pumb sets installed	358	2,106
3	Number of houses supplied with power	3,094	8,221
4	Number of Street lights electrified	40	1964
5	Number of industries electrified	68	165
6	Low tension transmission lines	147	380
7	High tension transmission lines	70	212
8	Number of distribution transformers	58	134 ¹⁸

Industries

The district has a number of major industrial units besides textiles, the other important industries in the district are leather turning match-manufacturing, Cotton ginning and the pressing. There are over 500 factories rice mills textile mills and printing presses. During the first and second plans the following schemes have been implemented under small scale industries in the Madurai district. Establishment of workshop -cum-servicing Centre for look industry cost of 8,00,000, Industrial colony Madurai cast of. 8.18 lakhs, Establishment of service cum training Centre for the manufacture of hurricane lantern at Palani cost of Rs. 4.72 lakhs and Probably spent of service Centre for that textiles mill pots with tools room section at Madurai cast of Rs.5.92 lakhs.

The industrial colony at Madurai is functioning since August 1958 with 19 industrial units and roughly Rs. 2 lakhs worth goods are manufactured here every month. The service centre for the manufacture of simple pots of textile mills was started in April 1959. The service centre for the manufacture of hurricane lanterns has gone into protection and, to start with containers or beginning manufactured. The village industries have also been resuscitated by plan schemes.¹⁹

Three training centres for carpentry and blacksmithy were started at the kovilpatti, Batlagundu and Neikkarapatti at a cost of Rs 74,000. Apart from this three protection centres are functioning at Dharmattupatti, Alanganallur and Thadicombu. A training-cum Production centre for pottery industry was established at Usilampatti for importing training in the manufacture of glazed pottery articles and white glaze articles and in the use of improved types of tools and kilns. This unit was opened in September 1958 and the cost of the schemes was Rs.30, 810. Five Flying Centres have been established in the Madurai district.

Two demonstrations units for manufacture of soaps with non-edible oil are functioning at Melur and Checkanurani. Upto March 1960, 38,194 ibs soaps Have been manufactured. The cost of the schemes was Rs.21,014. Two develop bee-keeping industry in Usilampatti block, bee-hives were distributed at half cost and Rs 5,625 was sanctioned for this scheme. So far 304 bee-hives have been distributed. Though sanctioned under First Plan the demonstrations – cum-protection Centre for handmade paper at the Gandhigram was started in Second Plan period and so far 45,889 of paper all varieties have been produced. Palm-gur manufacture is also an important village industry in the district and the government as well as the Khadi and village Industries Board gave substantial loans and grants for the cooperative societies engaged in this venture.²

A Handicrafts Sale society was established in Madurai and it was given a loan and a grant of rupees 5, 00 0 respectfully during 1956-57. Training centres for manufacturing ornamental handles, glass bangles and beads, art metal, artistic glassware were started during the Plans. In 1956-57 16 cases were given loans amounting to Rs.1,600 and in 1959-60, 723 cases were given loans to the tune of rupees 99, 520. Industrial cooperatives among small industrial numbered 3 in the district in 1950-51. In 1960-61 this number has risen to 28. The Central and State Governments have given a aid of Rs.5.02 lakhs and grant of Rs.38,250 respectively besides a loan of Rs.3.08 lakhs. The animal protection in this cooperatives is worth Rs.19.06 lakhs against Rs.2.54 lakhs before planning. The number of village industrial Co-operative Societies increased from 1 to 30 during the decade and the Government gave loans and grants of Rs.2.3 lakhs and

41,260 respectively. The protection through these societies was worth Rs.11,684 before 1950-51 and it has gone up to Rs.5.8 lakhs. With the start of one more Coir Society during the Second Plan period, there are four Coir Societies in the district. Goods produced in these societies are worth Rs.1.82,335.²¹ The progress of handloom weavers cooperatives during the two plans in the district is revealed by the following table.

Progress of Co-Operation among Handloom Weavers

S.No	Content	1950-51	1955-56	1960-61
1	Number of Societies	18	60	130
2	Number of looms	2,030	8,531	22,078
3	Number of weavers in co-operatives	4090	7,455	13,370

During the first plan period Rs.1.02 crores worth of goods were made and during the Second Plan period, this increased to Rs.3.38 crores. This shows the progress achieved by the weavers, Rs. Co-operative societies of the district. The government also gave substantial loan aid to them. Khadi Improvement Schemes was introduced at T. Kallupatti in Madurai district. In the year 1952.²² The progress of this industry is revealed by the following approximate figures.

Progress of Khadi Improvement Schemes

S.No	Year	No.of Weavers	No.of Spinners	Yards Produced Per Annum
1	1952	12	500	1,000
2	1955-56	50	1,000	10,000
3	1960-61	250	5,000	100,000

The every year Rs. 3.7 lakhs worth Khadi cloth is sold in the district. Ambar charkas schemes came into force in 1956. Training facilities in this chakra are widespread in the Madurai district. Several private industries have also been started during the planned. As year consequence of the improved power supply in the district.²³ There is however wider scope for further expansion of the industrial sector in the Madurai district.

Conclusion

Agriculture plays a pivotal role for the life of local population in general and the rural population in particular. The agricultural achievements such as major crops Rice, Cotton, Groundnut, Cumbu, Sugarcane, Oilseeds, Fruits, and development of Industries, Power Production, Irrigation system, Co-operative, Community development and allied sectors given top priority for the development during the First and Second Plan period from 1951-1961. The major crops like paddy, Sugarcane and has increased over the years in the district. In Madurai district towards crop diversification was given specialisation. Through the technology has dominant role play and as such adequate schemes and measures should be taken for propagating their innovate technologies in agriculture to the formers. The Government took initiate the steps for expansion in irrigation facilities, availability for production technology especially for small scale industries. The transport communication market infrastructure and processing facility for high value, crops should be strengthened around the Madurai district.

End Notes

- ¹P.K.Nampiyar, Census Report, Madurai District Hand Book, Government of Madras, 1950, P.54
- ²Ibid.,P.55.
- ³The Report on District Census, District Hand Book, Madurai, Vol-IX, 1961,P.40
- ⁴Ibid., P. 42.
- ⁵The Report on Second Five Year Plan 1956-61, Madurai District, Madras State Government press, Madras, 1966, P.14.
- ⁶Census Report on Madurai District, District hand book, Government of Madras 1961, P.15.
- ⁷G.O.NO.2591, Revenue department, Government of Madras, Dated on 17.10.60, P.4.
- ⁸Idem.
- ⁹The Report on Five Year Plan 1955, Madurai District, Madras State, Government Press, Madras, P.25.
- ¹⁰G.O.NO.17043A/PR/72/-3, Department of Rural and Finance, Government of Madras. Dated on 13.02.1966,P.6
- ¹¹Ibid.,PP.8-10.
- ¹²Report on Madras State Administration Report, 1957-58, Part-I, Government of Madras, P.197.
- ¹³The Report on Census of India 1961, Pocket Book Population Statistics, Census Centenary , New Delhi, 1962, P.18.
- ¹⁴G.O.NO. 447, Agricultural Department, Government of Madras, Dated on 18.05.1951, P.52.
- ¹⁵Ibid.,P.56
- ¹⁶G.O.NO. 1607, Agricultural Department, Government of Madras, Dated on 18.05.1960, P.18.
- ¹⁷The Report on Ministry of Agriculture, Primary Industry Training Guide, Part IV, New Delhi, 1961, P.15.
- ¹⁸Idem.
- ¹⁹A.P.Muthuswami, Census of India 1961, Serious-20 Tamil Nadu, Part-XIII-A, District Census HandBook, Village And Town Directary, Madurai, P.55.
- ²⁰A Report on Second Five Year Plan Commission, Madurai District, Madras State, Government Press, Madras, 1957, PP.88.
- ²¹The Report on Census of India 1961, Pocket Book Population Statistics, Op.Cit.108.
- ²²P.K.Nampiyar, Census Report , Madurai District Hand Book, Op.Cit. P.68.
- ²³Velavan C, Balaji P, Crop Diversification in Tamilnadu, - A Temporial analysis, Tamil Nadu Agricultural university, Coimbatore, 2012, pp.33-336.